

THE PROBLEM OF MODERN APPROACHES IN MATHEMATICS TEACHING

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Abstract: The article briefly analyzes the issue of the pedagogue's use of new methods to increase students' interest in reading and learning mathematics.

Key words: Mathematics, document, study, problem, independent work.

In some cases, the teacher should not only arouse interest in the students, but should not solve the learning problem by himself, and in other cases, he should guide the students in their independent work in solving the learning problem, as a result, the students will have the ability to gain knowledge independently and find new ways of mental action by making a hypothesis and proving it, and 56 Modern Approaches and Innovations in Mathematics Teaching module, the educational-methodological complex forms the skill of transferring knowledge from one problem to another, develops attention and imagination. Thus, the task of problem-based teaching is to cooperate in effective mastering of the system of knowledge and methods of mental and practical activities by students, to create in them the skills of creative application of the acquired knowledge in a new situation, to solve the problems of independence of knowledge and education and upbringing.

Conditions of problem-based teaching: - improving system of educational information; - choosing a method of solving the problem during the transfer of information to the educational task; - the subjective position of the learner, his understanding of the goals of knowledge and decision-making; - is able to evaluate the means at his disposal to solve the problem and achieve the result. Creative, semi-creative or heuristic, problem-based presentation of information, and presentation of information through problem-based initiation are the main methods

in the methodology of conducting educational activities based on problem-based teaching. When organizing a problem situation, it is necessary to take into account the following didactic goals: to attract the attention of students to the educational material, to arouse their interest in learning, to revive the cognitive activity of students, to bring them to the challenges of intellectual tension, the current knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students are related to the knowledge that will arise in the future. it is necessary to be able to show that they cannot meet their requirements, and to help students analyze educational problems and determine the most rational ways to solve them.

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2017 No. 187 "On approval of state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" was adopted in order to ensure continuity and consistency, to create a modern methodology, to improve the state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special vocational education based on a competence approach, to develop and implement a new generation of educational-methodological complexes.

The main tasks of teaching mathematics in general secondary education institutions: ensuring that students acquire knowledge and skills about mathematical concepts, properties, forms, methods and algorithms; understanding the importance of mathematics in human development and social development, socio-economic relations, training in the successful application of mathematical knowledge and skills in everyday life; formation of independent learning skills while developing individual characteristics of students; 66 The educational-methodological complex of the module of modern approaches and innovations in teaching mathematics consists of the formation of national and universal values, creativity in students, taking into account the integration of subjects, and directing them to consciously choose a profession.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following basic competences are formed in accordance with their age characteristics, based on the continuity and coherence of education, the priority of the student's personality and interests. Communicative

competence means the ability to interact in social situations in one's native language and in any foreign language, to follow the culture of communication, social flexibility, and the ability to work effectively in a team. Competence to work with information means to find the necessary information from media sources, sort, process, store, use them effectively, ensure their security, and develop the ability to acquire media culture. Self-development competence - continuous physical, spiritual, mental, intellectual and creative development of oneself, striving for perfection

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